

CURRENT SITUATION OF USING ALTERNATIVE WAYS OF ASSESSMENT AT SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract. *This article provides a brief introduction to assessment and discusses the importance of assessment in education. The opinions of scholars about assessment and the significance and application of alternative assessment are also discussed. The categories of alternative assessment are given and their application is also discussed. In addition, the opinions of teachers and students about the new formative and summative assessment introduced into practice in current schools are given, as well as their effectiveness and shortcomings.*

Keywords: *assessment, formative, summative, alternative assessment categories.*

Introduction

Assessment is the process of defining information about a pupil's learning, expertise and progress. It is a tool for teachers to know how learners achieve the goal and how teaching methods are working. Today, changes are taking place in all areas of our society, rapid developments are taking place to meet world standards. We can also find such changes in the educational system and assessment methods. Kamola Muradkasimova, Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences, gives the following thoughts about changes in the assessment process: "As, the world development progressed, the evolution of assessment also continued to progress. Thus, the methods of testing the knowledge vary through the history, but besides the changes the outcome was developing and educating skillful specialists" [1;173]. These days many secondary schools are being changed from traditional assessment to alternative ones.

These new types of assessment have been developed and are being introduced into the education system. The new assessment system will bring great developments to the education system and will be of great importance in the development of the future generation as more advanced and competent professionals in their field. We can cite formative and summative assessment. These assessment types appeared in world pedagogy in the 60s-70s of the 20th century (Michael Scriven, Benjamin Bloom). In Uzbekistan, as part of modern educational reforms, in particular, to modernize school education, they began to be widely used after the 2010s and have now become a key part of the national curriculum. In the presented article, we would like to write about current alternative ways of assessment at schools and its effects on learning process.

Methodology

Alternative assessment is used to measure a learner's expertise and proficiency. It develops the learner's critical thinking, creativity and autonomy. There is no specific categorization of alternative assessments but scholars Lombardi, Reeves, Simonsonetal typically divide alternative assessment into authentic assessment, performance-based assessment, and constructivist assessment. In authentic assessment, students are assigned to real-life, meaningful tasks that require them to make use of the knowledge they have gained to complete the tasks. Performance-

based evaluation observes the ability of students to use higher-order thinking skills (HOTS) while doing tasks and how they apply the skills that they have learned. Lastly, students are assigned tasks to examine their mastery of certain skills through constructivist assessment. Ghaffar and Yusop (2018) who divide alternative assessment into five categories of assessments: peer and self-assessment, group-based assessment, performance-based assessment, portfolio-based assessment, and technology-based assessment [2;3].

In the current era, as a result of the development and widespread use of information technology, such changes and improvements are also needed in the education sector. Assessment methods in the education systems of foreign countries are being used as a pilot project and, if they show effective results, are being used in practice. So new alternative assessment types like formative and summative assessment have been put into practice. Formative assessment is used to evaluate a pupil's learning process during the term. In classrooms, formative assessment refers to frequent, interactive assessments of student's progress and understanding to identify learners' needs and adjust teaching appropriately [3;261]. In this case, the student is evaluated on a scale of 1 to 10 based on their participation and activity in class during the academic quarter. Formative assessment methods are necessary to raise overall levels of student's achievement. Quantitative and qualitative research on formative assessment are proved as one of the most important interventions for promoting high-performance ever studied [4;261].

Analysis and discussion

Summative assessment is used to evaluate a pupil's learning journey at the end of term and learners' progress is checked by tests and project works, midterm exams, final project, papers, teacher-designed tests, standardized tests, and high-stakes tests. Summative assessment is an appraisal of learning at the end of an instructional unit or at a specific point in time. It compares student knowledge or skills against standards or benchmarks [5;1]. As a subset of summative assessment, standardized tests play a pivotal role in ensuring that schools are held to the same standards and that all students regardless of race or socio-economic background perform to expectations. Summative assessment provides educators with the metrics to know what's working and what's not [6;1]. Summative assessment is used as following:

-summative assessment (BSB) - a process of formal assessment of the level of mastery of the established competencies at the end of a chapter, section;

-summative assessment (CHSB) - a process of formal assessment of the level of mastery of the established competencies at the end of a quarter;

-Project work.

If we take summative assessment based on a 100-point system, then in the range of 100-86 points, the child will receive 5 marks, in the range of 86-65 points - 4 marks, in the range of 65-45 points - 3 marks. ChSB is set in the amount of quarters available in the year. That is, the student passes 4 times a year or 2 times a year in some subjects (taken once a week). ChSB consists of 40 points during one academic year, BSB consists of 50 points.

In order to identify the new assessment types' bad and good sides and influences on teaching and learning process, we conducted a questionnaire among teachers and 10-11 grade pupils. Here are some teacher and pupils' views in the following.

Gulzar (secondary school teacher) says that the new assessment types are the best ones for me and I would recommend it to other schools to use this kind of new assessment type. Guljamal (English teacher) comments that summative assessment allows for the comparison of student performance. This description allows for the comparison of students with each other, the

determination of the level of knowledge acquired by students, and the comparison of educational programs. Formative assessment allows students to express their opinions and teaches them to make informed judgments and decisions about the growth of acquired knowledge.

Juldiz observes that since the assessment types has been used at her school, pupils are eager to learn more in order not to get low mark but it is somehow difficult assessment type. Malika is proud of the new assessment methods as it provided her with a clear and fair measure of her students' achievements at the end of a course or program. Biybinaz states that we may call the new assessment methods as "Motivation for students" because the results of a final assessment can motivate students to engage with the material but the bad side of this new assessment types is I have to print test materials on paper at my own expense and fills out report folders is a burden for me.

Xan-sayat (pupil) says this new assessment is good but difficult for her and previous was simple. Kiz jibek (pupil) concludes that she likes the new assessment type but it is hard to achieve the mark needed. As Yaqipkarim states, previous assessment method was simple, current one is difficult and new extra assessment type should be included to the lesson.

Conclusion

To conclude, we are not mistaken in saying that assessment is important in education from the opinions of the above-mentioned scholars and that assessment is a bridge that connects teachers and students. From our survey, we understood that while new assessment serves to enhance and strengthen students' knowledge in the educational process, we have witnessed that this type of assessment causes difficulties for some students and teachers. Today's learners need more expertise as advanced technologies required it. Nowadays learners want to apply the things learnt in real life situations. They want to communicate freely, share their opinions, catch up with up-to-date technological period. In addition, teachers of this assessment method can bring up pupils who are able to communicate fluently in English everyday situations.

Necessarily, the current assessment system can lead learners to gain knowledge deeply, use it in everyday situation, comprehend critical thinking and contribute to their future professional development.

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